

Understanding the bullet evolution and its interaction with dielectrics in a capillary helium plasma jet

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In the last two decades, the atmospheric pressure plasma jet has gained much attention, due to its low production cost and the wide range of applications such as plasma medicine, local surface modification, local sterilization etc. The plasma jet device has been extensively studied and significant understanding has been gained through analytical/simulation models and experiments. However, deep understanding of the detailed mechanisms of plasma jet evolution and its interaction with material surfaces needs further research.

A two dimensional axisymmetric plasma fluid model was used [1], in order to study the evolution and interaction of a capillary helium plasma jet with a dielectric surface. In Figure 1, the plasma jet device and the distribution of air concentration in the domain are presented. The results of the simulation have been verified with experimental results.

The simulation results showed that (during the discharge) the plasma bullet propagates towards the dielectric surface and has a torus like shape centred on the axis of symmetry of the tube. When the plasma bullet almost reaches ($\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$) the dielectric, its propagation continues tangentially along the dielectric surface. For the interpretation of the results, the most important reaction pathways for the plasma bullet propagation have been studied, as well as the dependence of these reactions on the electric field and the level of air concentration in the domain. This fundamental analysis provides useful insight behind the evolution and interaction of the plasma bullet with dielectric surfaces, which is an important prerequisite for developing and optimizing existing applications of the plasma jet.

Figure 1: Simulation domain of the capillary plasma jet device and the level of air concentration (ppm) in the domain.

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